

Defining procedures and services to enforce data provenance for thematic communities and beyond

Introduction

Due to the increasing complexity of data analysis workflows, provenance management is a key component to support the re-use of scientific data. Alongside findability, accessibility and interoperability, the reusability of data constitutes a pillar of the FAIR principles and in this regard rich and reliable provenance is essential to ensure that.

To enable a well-defined data provenance in the scientific experiment's workflows, from data production to data usage, this task:

- ★ elaborate cross-domain, FAIR-oriented procedures and recommendations to enforce data provenance by taking into account needs coming from various communities such as **nanoscience/soft matter, material science** and **climate change** in the field of environmental science;
- ★ implement these procedures and recommendations by developing the proper adaptations/extensions on top of existing scientific data services, made available by the participating partners at national level.

In such a context, the W3C PROV standard has been considered as a recommended family of specifications for tracking processes and responsibilities as well as describing provenance structures within complex experiments and large workflows on scientific data.

Challenges addressed

The overall objective of the use case is to enhance provenance capabilities, thus addressing FAIR-oriented full provenance management.

For the material science/nanoscience community, we focused on the wide community behind the [NFFA-Europe PILOT Project \(NEP\)](#). We planned to **define general procedures and recommendations** on how to manage the aspect of data provenance for the NEP users' community and beyond.

In the climate science domain provenance management plays a key role both for numerical end-to-end simulations at the data center level as well as in the inner data analytics workflows. In such a context, two distinct demonstrators have been implemented to showcase how to manage provenance tracking at two different levels, thus addressing open science challenges (shareability, reusability, etc.) at a finer granularity.

Benefits through EOSC-Pillar

The material science use case will benefit through EOSC-Pillar by the fact that the NEP user community and the project itself can **establish a strong connection with the EOSC network**, favouring a continuous exchange among the two communities. Such exchange is of mutual interest: on one side (NEP) allowing the project and the data services built within the project to be EOSC-compliant. On the other hand, EOSC can benefit from **a large and committed user community** that should provide useful suggestions and case studies in the overall EOSC implementation.

USE CASE

WEBSITE LINK

[ENES Climate Analytics Service](#)
[Ophidia data analytics framework](#)

[TriDAS](#)

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COMMUNITIES

· Research communities
Climate science
Material science/
Nanoscience

June 2022

PARTNERS

The climate use cases have been integrated into the [EOSCPillar4EarthScience](#) D4Science VRE as well as the [ENES Climate Analytics Service](#), which is the server-side compute infrastructure exploited in [Use Case 2](#). In this way scientific users can run their climate data science notebooks and get fine-grained provenance information based on W3C prov specifications. This allows users to retrieve the data lineage of an object including the entire analytics workflow associated to it, thus addressing FAIR principles at a finer granularity.

Highlights

Material science/nanoscience case study

The case study within the community of material science/nanoscience is represented by data management practices and services developed for making FAIR compliant a scientific archive of Scanning Tunneling Microscopy (STM) images [1]. The main objective was to provide guidelines and recommendations on how to manage the aspect of the provenance of a scientific archive

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USE CASE

of Scanning Tunneling Microscopy (STM) images. Nevertheless, services and tools designed to improve the overall value of the dataset of STM images by implementing different aspects of the FAIR principles were provided. On top of them, during the FAIRification workflow, was applied the W3C PROV standard to describe the provenance of metadata, from the original STM images to the ones curated and available on the TriDAS website.

The web service workflow, allows users a first exploration of the dataset which then should be downloaded for further analysis and image visualization. The scatter plot features the selection of a specific metadata combination to retrieve a new page containing a table with metadata fields for each image in that subset. On this page, researchers can select, order, filter, and search images based on their metadata values. The ID column consists of each image's unique identifier in the database and, by clicking on it, the corresponding STM image is rendered and shown on a new page, where a download feature is included to obtain data, metadata, plot, and provenance metadata for every image.

Climate science

In the climate science domain, two distinct demonstrators have been implemented to address provenance tracking at two different levels:

- ★ the first one (first-level) refers to the whole end-to-end scientific workflow including a proper reference to input and output datasets via PIDs;
- ★ the second one (second-level) provides a focus on some first-level tasks, like those ones regarding data analytics which can be represented themselves as a workflow of micro-tasks (analytics

operators) which may usually be in the order of hundreds or thousands.

The main idea is to navigate the first level provenance to have a complete understanding of the overall high-level end-to-end workflow and then have the opportunity to drill-down into some specific analytics tasks to get more detailed information about their internal workflow in terms of micro-tasks or analytics operators. The first demonstrator provides a set of easy-to-use templates and tools that can be used in the context of climate science notebooks to enable researchers to provide standards conforming provenance descriptions for their data products.

The second demonstrator is mainly aimed at scientific users from the core climate modelling community, who are interested in performing scientific data analysis workflows with a stronger provenance support (so called second-level) able to track analytics activity at the level of single operators.

Links to relevant materials

- [1] Tommaso Rodani, Elda Osmenaj, Alberto Cazzaniga, Mirco Panighel, Cristina Africh, & Stefano Cozzini. (2021). Dataset of Scanning Tunneling Microscopy (STM) images of graphene on nickel (1,1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5808724>
- [2] A Templating System to Generate Provenance, Luc Moreau et al. IEEE Transactions on software engineering, <https://nms.kcl.ac.uk/luc.moreau/papers/provtemplate-tse17.pdf>
- [3] S. Fiore, D. Elia, C. Palazzo, F. Antonio, A. D'Anca, I. Foster, G. Aloisio, "Towards High Performance Data Analytics for Climate Change", ISC High Performance 2019, LNCS Springer, 2019

The web service workflow on the TriDAS website.

Fine-grained provenance information captured at the second level of the multi-model Precipitation Trend Analysis (PTA) analytics workflow based on W3C PROV specifications

